

FUNCTIONS OF ANTHROPNOMS IN LITERARY TEXT

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ABSTRACT

This article deals with the notion of anthroponyms, which refer to lexico-grammatical class of nouns and which are one of the most important components in lexical system of any languages. Anthroponyms cannot exist by their own, they are significative of historical development of civilization, the impact of some historical events and people, society, culture and family, thereby reflecting language picture of the world. Appearing as one of the significant inner linguistical means of text formation anthroponyms can be the key of interpretation of literary text.

Anthroponym is a proper name or a complex of proper names identifying a person. Generally, it is a name of any person: real or fictional. In other words, anthroponyms are personal names of people. A personal name is a name of a person, given to him at birth or chosen by an adult person for himself. The most important difference between personal name and other anthroponyms and proper names is individualization of the object.

Proper names play a considerable role in lexis of any language. Linguists are still interested in researching of proper names and their roles in language. An author can make a particular sense in literary text, and this sense with the right interpretation is able to help to solve all the mystery of each character included by the author.

Specificity of proper names has always attracted the attention of linguists, philologists, geographers, interpreters, culturologists, historians, translators and other researches. This is mostly linked with the fact that proper names, where a significant place is occupied by anthroponyms, are the most important components of language and conceptual picture of the world.

The analysis of anthological system of literary text allows to state the fact that in researching of anthroponym functions in literary text, most of all, it is vital to consider the variety of complicated connections and relations.

In the process of giving proper names to their characters authors of literary text achieve various aims, and one of them is to persuade readers towards one understanding or another, towards one assessment of various sides of reality or another, to influence readers and direct their feelings according to the author's concept. Therefore, the interpretation of functions of

anthroponyms and their purpose in literary text is very important problem. Anthroponomic model of literary text is only formed by the author's attitude, however this model acquires real features only if it is oriented on linguistic connotative potential of names.

In any literary text an image of literary hero is connected with his name and the image of this character endowed with appropriate features appears in reader's consciousness. While reading reader makes various association connected with names of characters, these proper names can attract or even create emotional atmosphere in literary text.

Names of literary characters are not chosen accidentally. Their meaning, forms and situations of usage are connected with artistic and visual means which are created by the author of literary text. Thus, literary anthroponym expresses subtext information, concentrated all necessary figurative meanings into itself, reflects the author's position and helps to transmit a hidden meaning to the reader.

Literary text is a unique place of proper names connection. Appearing as an element of literary text, proper names contribute to various meanings which are involved in the literary text. And sometimes the author of literary text doesn't realize this variety. There is an appropriate necessity in the name, which an author gives to his character, and perhaps it is not visible for the author himself.

Specificity of figurative and artistic comprehension of word effect to the function of proper names, involved in the literary text. In the text proper names undergo functional reconstruction, and not only nominative, but also characterizing is major. In this way, the research of proper name involves the investigation of principals and ways to nominate characters, stylistic functions of proper names, their connections, linked with author's ideas, the idea of literary text and realization of specific image.

All the literary anthroponyms can be classified into three groups:

- Proper names completely borrowed from already existed in the culture;
- Anthroponyms with sound-graphic borrowed part;
- Anthroponyms completely created by the author.

In general, the research of names in the work of appropriate writer is interesting and significant, so far as proper name contains literary finds, stylistic influence, and then the reader's worldview appears. So far as the main content of literary text is a person, so the connection between ways of representation, viewpoint and words choice is evident in the naming of the characters. Therefore, appropriate functional issues of anthroponyms in literary text are taking place.

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